

1 **Simultaneous application of vacuum and sweep gas in a polypropylene membrane**
2 **contactor for the recovery of dissolved methane from water**

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9 **Abstract**

10 Vacuum and nitrogen as sweep gas were used simultaneously (combination mode) to generate
11 the driving force in a microporous polypropylene membrane contactor for the recovery of
12 dissolved methane from water. Experiments were carried out under different liquid flow-rates
13 (5.0 to 28.0 L h⁻¹), N₂ flow-rates (0.5 to 1.5 L h⁻¹) and vacuum pressures (0 to 480 mbar). The
14 maximum removal efficiency of methane was >90% at moderate values of gas-to-liquid ratios
15 (G/L) and vacuum of 0.2 and ≤200 mbar, respectively. Removal efficiencies obtained in
16 combination mode were usually higher than when using vacuum or sweep gas, separately. To
17 achieve a methane content >35% in the recovered gas, G/L values lower than 0.03 are
18 necessary, with removal efficiency up to 55%. Even at these soft conditions, gas phase mass
19 transfer resistance was demonstrated as being negligible, so the limiting resistance was in the
20 liquid phase. G/L ratios increased until values of 0.3, with a vacuum of 200 mbar, maximised
21 the energy output (>250 kJ m⁻³ of treated water), in the case of recovered methane mixed with
22 biogas produced in an anaerobic reactor. The results show that combination mode could be
23 used to improve the performance of methane degassing in membrane contactors.

24 **Keywords**

25 Combination mode operation; Methane degassing; Mass transfer; Energy analysis;
26 Greenhouse gas emission

27

28 **Highlights**

- 29
- Best performance in combination mode rather than vacuum or sweep gas separately
- 30
- Methane recovery >90% achieved under moderate vacuum and sweep gas flow-rate
- 31
- Gas CH₄ content >35%, needed for microturbines, achievable at soft G/L and vacuum
- 32
- Liquid phase conditions dominate the overall mass transfer resistance
- 33
- Positive energy balance from recovered methane is achieved in combination mode

34

35 **1. Introduction**

36 Methane emissions have an important effect on the global atmospheric greenhouse gas (GHG)
37 concentration, not least because its global-warming potential (GWP) is 28 times higher than
38 carbon dioxide (100 years horizon) [1]. Additionally, in the presence of nitrogen oxides
39 tropospheric methane oxidation leads to the formation of health-damaging tropospheric
40 ozone. In this regard, methane concentrations have notably increased over the last decade,
41 which can be mainly related to anthropogenic sources, about 50% greater than natural sources
42 [2]. Indeed, methane emissions represent 10 to 15% of global GHG emissions [3] whose
43 origins can be found in agriculture and livestock (49%), manufacture of fossil fuel (33%),
44 solid urban waste (11%) and wastewater treatment (7%) in 2019 [4], with an average annual
45 emission of 0.3 Gt [1].

46 In recent years, anaerobic wastewater treatment plants have received special attention due to
47 the simultaneous production of biogas as the most attractive second-generation biofuel.
48 Biogas can supply 13.5 MJ COD⁻¹ removed (1.5 kWh with 40% efficiency) [5], achieving a
49 self-sufficient process [6], and a negative carbon footprint for an expanded granular sludge
50 bed (EGSB) reactor has also been reported [7]. Anaerobic treatment offers multiple
51 advantages over aerobic processes: lower requirements of volume and nutrients, lower energy
52 requirements (lack of aeration) and lower sludge production. On the contrary, the anaerobic
53 effluent has high amounts of dissolved methane (D-CH₄), so once the effluent is discharged,
54 fugitive emissions of methane take place, contributing to the most important source of GHG
55 emissions in wastewater treatment plants [8]. These methane emissions involve the loss of a
56 potential energy source, environmental problems and an explosive atmosphere if methane
57 concentration is above the lower flammable limit (5%) in a confined space [9]. In this regard,
58 the water discharged with a relatively low D-CH₄ concentration of 1.4 mg L⁻¹ can result in a

59 CH₄ content in air of 5% at 15°C and atmospheric pressure (estimated from Henry's Law
60 [10]), when spontaneous degasification occurs in a confined space, such as closed vessels or
61 sewers.

62 Estimates of D-CH₄ losses through anaerobic effluent can represent between 11% and 88% of
63 the total methane produced in the anaerobic reactor for low strength wastes [6]. Some benefits
64 of methane removal from the anaerobic effluent have been reported, for example better
65 sedimentation of the anaerobic particles by means of dissolution of methane microbubbles
66 [11] and higher COD removal efficiency by reducing the dissolved H₂ content in the liquid
67 phase [12]. Recovered methane from the anaerobic effluents can also be a potential energy
68 source, which could be directly stored with the biogas collected from the bioreactor.

69 Hollow fibre membrane contactors (HFMC) have emerged as a promising alternative for
70 degasification of liquid streams where the transport of the gas molecules takes place through
71 the membrane wall without contact or dispersion of one phase into the other. These HFMC
72 are able to achieve high removal efficiencies of dissolved gases, with very compact units
73 since they show high volumetric mass transfer coefficients. The HFMC avoids the flooding,
74 foaming and emulsion problems commonly observed in direct contact units, such as packing
75 columns and spray aerators [13–15], resulting in an easier and economically advantageous
76 process. Membranes have been implemented extensively in recent years, due to the huge
77 variety of available membrane contactors and their versatility for any application [16–20]. In
78 this regard, the methane degassing in anaerobic liquid effluents with HFMC has received
79 increasing research attention [6] and studies showing the viability of this technology operating
80 in vacuum [7,11] or sweep gas mode [19,21,22] have recently been reported.

81 HFMC can operate in vacuum or sweep gas mode, in order to generate a partial pressure
82 gradient of the solute as the driving force. On the one hand, when only vacuum is applied,

83 high purity gas methane can be obtained whilst methane is diluted at sweep gas mode. On the
84 other hand, vacuum mode shows the greatest energy consumption, even though the recovered
85 gas methane can be directly used for thermal and electricity production without previous
86 concentration [23]. As an alternative to overcome the drawbacks of each operation mode,
87 vacuum and sweep gas can be used simultaneously.

88 In spite of the considerable amount of references to industrial applications of water degassing
89 via combination vacuum and sweep gas processing with HFMC [24–26], mainly removing
90 dissolved oxygen, only a few studies have reported results for this combination mode [27,28].
91 In this regard, the work of Kartohardjono et al. [27] focused only on a mass transfer analysis,
92 while the study of Martić et al. [28] was interested in the influence of the purity of nitrogen
93 (as sweep gas) in the de-oxygenating of water, showing the effectiveness of HFMC in the
94 operation (with removal efficiencies of approximately 99%), and estimating that the cost of
95 the combination process with HFMC was significant lower (~50%) than conventional
96 degassing processes. Taking into account this scarce information, it seems that studies on the
97 combination mode are needed to enhance and deepen the knowledge of this technology,
98 which could be especially suitable in cases of methane degassing applications.

99 Since there is no available data in the literature about membrane operation in combination
100 mode for the degassing of methane from water, the main aim of this work was to evaluate the
101 performance of a microporous polypropylene HFMC operating by means of both vacuum and
102 sweep gas simultaneously for methane recovery. This represents the extension of our previous
103 studies [29,30], where both modes were studied independently with the same HFMC. For this
104 purpose, the methane removal performance from a synthetic water stream containing D-CH₄
105 under different operational and hydraulic conditions was analysed, by varying the liquid flow-
106 rate, vacuum pressure and sweep gas flow-rate in short-term experiments. Also, the effect of

107 the combination mode on the mass transfer and feasibility for energy production from the
108 recovered methane stream has been determined.

109 **2. Materials and methods**

110 *2.1. Experimental setup and procedure*

111 A synthetic D-CH₄ water stream was used to carry out demethanization tests in this work.
112 This stream was obtained from a packed-bed absorption column by using de-ionised water
113 (<1 μS cm⁻¹) and 99.5%_v CH₄ (Carbueros Metálicos, Spain) flowing in counter-current. The
114 column was built in methacrylate with an inner diameter of 6.5 cm, an effective height of 50.0
115 cm and filled with polypropylene Pall Rings of 1" (Refilltech, Germany). The CH₄ flow-rate
116 was fixed at 1000 mL min⁻¹ using a mass flow controller (Bronkhorst Hi-Tec, The
117 Netherlands). With the absorption column system, the mean concentration of CH₄ in the
118 liquid effluent was 21.65 ± 0.62 mg L⁻¹, similar to values reported by other authors
119 [21,22,31,32] . This value represents the 95% saturation of CH₄ in water (22.81 mg L⁻¹ at
120 25°C [10]). CH₄ oversaturation in the water did not take place, in contrast to what is observed
121 in real anaerobic effluents, where oversaturation was frequently reported [6]. The total
122 volume of the system was 1.5 L of water and the total operation time of each experiment was
123 1 hour, until a steady-state condition was reached.

124 Synthetic D-CH₄ water column effluent was introduced to the HFMC. Fig. 1 shows the
125 flowchart of the experimental system used to carry out the degassing tests and evaluate the
126 membrane performance. Experiments were carried out at room temperature (23°C ± 3°C).
127 Synthetic water was used in this study in order to prevent the potential interference of
128 suspended or soluble compounds in the performance of the system. Long-term performance of

129 the same PP membrane contactor treating the anaerobic effluent of an EGSB reactor was
130 reported in a previous work [30].

131
132 *Fig. 1. Flowchart of the degassing system, including the packed column for the saturation,*
133 *sweep gas and vacuum generation equipment, sampling points and the hollow fibre*
134 *membrane contactor*

135
136 In our experimental setup, water operated in a closed loop. Thus, water was recirculated in the
137 system by using a peristaltic pump (Watson-Marlow, EE.UU.), with liquid flow-rates (Q_L , L
138 h^{-1}) ranging from 5.0 to 28.0 L h^{-1} .

139 In a typical test, the system was run without the operation of the HFMC (gas ports were
140 closed) in an initial pre-start period, to ensure that the effluent from the column reached a
141 stable value near saturation. After this, membrane gas ports were opened and the N_2 mass
142 flow controller and the vacuum system were simultaneously switched on. The desired N_2
143 flow-rate and vacuum pressure stabilized in less than one minute and the degassing process

144 started. As an example, in Fig. 2 a typical pattern of the liquid and gas outlet methane
145 concentrations in HFMC is shown. As can be seen, stable behaviour was observed after 20 to
146 30 minutes of HFMC operation. The results presented in this work were those obtained when
147 this steady state performance was reached.

148 In HFMC, duplicate liquid samples were collected at the inlet and outlet ports and gas
149 samples were taken from the outlet gas port, which contained the recovered methane (R-CH₄).
150 All samples were collected without the samples being exposed to the atmosphere.

151
152 *Fig. 2. Pattern of the concentration of methane at the liquid (C_{L2}) and gas (C_{G2}) outlet of the*
153 *hollow fibre membrane contactor (HFMC) in a typical test. Operational conditions: sweep*
154 *gas mode, Q_{N2} = 26.0 L h⁻¹ and Q_L = 13.7 L h⁻¹*

155
156 The liquid samples were analysed by using the head-space method described previously
157 [7,11,29]. Briefly, 50 mL of liquid samples were collected and injected in sealed vials of 125
158 mL, prefilled with air. These vials were kept in an orbital shaker at 150 rpm and 25°C for 1.5
159 hours (to ensure gas-liquid equilibrium). After this, 0.5 mL of the head-space gas was injected
160 into a gas chromatograph (Agilent GC 7820A, Spain) equipped with Agilent HP-PLOT/U and

161 Agilent HP-MOLESIEVE and a thermal conductivity detector. In order to determine the
162 methane concentration in the liquid sample, it was necessary to apply Henry's Law:

$$163 \quad H^{cp} = \frac{C_{L,eq}}{p^{p,eq} \cdot M_{CH_4}} \quad (1)$$

164 where $C_{L,eq}$ ($\text{mg L}^{-1} \equiv \text{g m}^{-3}$) is the methane concentration in the liquid in equilibrium with the
165 head-space gas, $P^{p,eq}$ (Pa) is the partial pressure of the CH_4 in the head-space in equilibrium
166 with the liquid phase, M_{CH_4} is the molecular weight of the CH_4 (16 g mol^{-1}) and H^{cp} is the
167 Henry's Law constant, expressed in $\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$. The value of H^{cp} is $1.4 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ at
168 25°C [10]. So, the methane concentration in the original liquid sample was determined from:

$$169 \quad C_L = \frac{C_{G,eq} \cdot V_G + C_{L,eq} \cdot V_L}{V_L} \quad (2)$$

170 where C_L and $C_{G,eq}$ (mg L^{-1}) is the methane concentration in the original sample and in the
171 head-space of the analysis vials, respectively, and V_G and V_L (L) is the gas and liquid volume
172 inside the analysis vials, respectively.

173 The performance of the CH_4 recovery process was evaluated through the removal efficiency
174 of methane (RE, %) which is defined as:

$$175 \quad \text{RE} = \frac{C_{L1} - C_{L2}}{C_{L1}} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

176 where C_{L1} and C_{L2} (mg L^{-1}) is the methane concentration in the inlet and outlet liquid from the
177 HFMC, respectively. In Eq. (3) a negligible variation of the liquid volume flow-rate was
178 assumed.

179 A sampling point was used to take 0.5 mL of HFMC outlet gas samples, by means of a gas
180 chromatography syringe, which were injected into the former gas chromatograph. Moisture
181 content of the recovered gas was measured using a hygrometer (model HygroPalm-HP21,
182 (Rotronic Instruments, Switzerland). The moisture of the recovered gas was close to

183 saturation point in the whole range of sweep-gas flow rate tested (0.5 to 1.5 L h⁻¹), with a
184 value of relative humidity >90%, which correspond to a H₂O content close to 3% at standard
185 conditions.

186 To verify the absence of membrane fouling or malfunction, a control test was carried out
187 weekly. A mean deviation of 0.83% was obtained, confirming that the HFMC maintained its
188 performance during this study.

189

190 *2.2 Degassing membrane contactor*

191 A commercial polypropylene (PP) hollow fibre membrane contactor (1x5.5 MiniModule,
192 Liqui-Cel, Membrane GmbH, Germany) with a microporous and hydrophobic structure was
193 selected to develop this study. The main features of the membrane are summarised in Table 1.
194 This HFMC was considered to be representative of the membranes in real industrial
195 applications and it has been used in previous studies [29,30].

196 The HFMC was operated in lumen side mode, where experiments were carried out with the
197 liquid flowing in the lumen side and vacuum or sweep gas applied in the shell side, and in
198 counter-current flow. Liquid flow-rate (Q_L) was varied between 5.0 and 28.0 L h⁻¹, with a
199 pressure drop ranging from 40 to 60 mbar. N₂ (99.9%_{ov}, Carbueros Metálicos, Spain) was used
200 as sweep gas, with a flow-rate (Q_{N_2}) ranging from 0.5 to 1.5 L h⁻¹ adjusted by means of a
201 mass flow controller (Bronkhorst Hi-Tec, The Netherlands). Under these operational
202 conditions, the gas-to-liquid ratio (G/L) varied from 0.012 to 0.302. Vacuum was generated
203 by using a water jet pump (VWR, Spain). The applied vacuum pressure (P_{vac}) ranged from 0
204 to 480 mbar (manometric pressure was from 0 to -480 mbar) and it was measured with a
205 digital manometer (Kimo MP112, Kimo Instruments, France) at the inlet and outlet of the
206 membrane contactor to ensure stable vacuum along the module.

207 *Table 1. Characteristics of the PP membrane contactor (provided by the manufacturer)*

Property	Value
Structure	Microporous
Shell tube inner diameter, m	0.025
Module length, m	0.176
Number of fibres	2300
Effective length (L), m	0.1132
Inner diameter (d _i), μm	220
Outer diameter (d _o), μm	300
Effective internal area (A _i), m ²	0.180
Effective external area (A _e), m ²	0.245
Pore diameter, μm	0.04
Porosity	0.4
Tortuosity	1.4
Packing fraction	0.33
Maximum liquid flow-rate (Q _L), L h ⁻¹	30
Maximum sweep gas flow-rate (Q _{N2}), L h ⁻¹	800

208 *2.3. Mass transfer evaluation*

209 The mass transfer of the separation process was evaluated in the liquid-membrane-gas system.

210 For this purpose, the overall experimental mass transfer coefficient (K_{L,exp}, m s⁻¹) was

211 calculated from the following differential mass balance applied to the liquid phase [33]:

212
$$Q_l \cdot \frac{dC}{dA} = -K_L \cdot (\Delta C_{lm}) \quad (4)$$

213 The integration resulting from Eq. (4) is as follows [34]:

214
$$K_{L,exp} = \frac{Q_l}{A_L} \frac{C_{L2} - C_{L1}}{\Delta C_{lm}} \quad (5)$$

215 ΔC_{lm} is defined as [34]:

216
$$\Delta C_{lm} = \frac{(C_{L2}^* - C_{L2}) - (C_{L1}^* - C_{L1})}{\ln\left(\frac{C_{L2}^* - C_{L2}}{C_{L1}^* - C_{L1}}\right)} \quad (6)$$

217 where A_L (m²) is the interfacial area in contact with the liquid phase, Q_l (m³ s⁻¹) is the liquid

218 flow-rate and C_{L1}^{*} and C_{L2}^{*} (mg L⁻¹) are the methane concentration in the liquid in

219 equilibrium with the methane content in the outlet gas (C_{G2}, mg L⁻¹) and inlet gas (C_{G1} = 0 mg

220 L^{-1}), respectively, calculated from Henry's Law ($C_L^* = C_G/H$, H being the dimensionless
 221 Henry's constant; a value of 29.55 at 25°C [10]). With the liquid flowing in lumen side mode,
 222 A_L is the membrane's internal area (A_i). The mass transfer can also be evaluated through the
 223 overall experimental mass transfer resistance ($R_{ov,exp}$, $s\ m^{-3}$):

$$224 \quad R_{ov,exp} = \frac{1}{K_{L,exp} \cdot A_L} \quad (7)$$

225 The overall resistance for a hydrophobic, microporous membrane with gas filled pores
 226 consists of three resistances in series: the liquid phase boundary layer ($R_{L,est}$), the membrane
 227 ($R_{m,est}$), and the gaseous phase boundary layer ($R_{G,est}$). The estimated overall mass transfer
 228 resistance ($R_{ov,est}$) can be obtained by adding the partial resistances in series. Thus, in a
 229 cylindrical geometry like in the HFMC, the overall resistance can be described by means of
 230 the equation:

$$231 \quad R_{ov,est} = R_{L,est} + R_{m,est} + R_{G,est} = \frac{1}{k_L \cdot A_L} + \frac{1}{H \cdot k_m \cdot A_{ml}} + \frac{1}{H \cdot k_G \cdot A_G} = \frac{1}{K_{L,est} \cdot A_L} \quad (8)$$

232 where k_G , k_m and k_L ($m\ s^{-1}$) stand for the individual mass transfer coefficients in the gas,
 233 membrane and liquid, respectively, $K_{L,est}$ ($m\ s^{-1}$) is the estimated overall mass transfer
 234 coefficient, A_G and A_L (m^2) are the membrane surfaces in contact with gas and liquid,
 235 respectively, and A_{ml} (m^2) is the logarithmic mean membrane surface.

236 The k_L value can be estimated from the Leveque equation [35] with the liquid flowing in the
 237 lumen side:

$$238 \quad k_L = 1.62 \cdot \frac{D_{L,CH_4}}{d_i} \cdot \left(\frac{d_i^2 \cdot v_L}{D_{L,CH_4} \cdot L} \right)^{1/3} \quad (9)$$

239 where v_L ($m\ s^{-1}$) is the liquid velocity and D_{L,CH_4} ($m^2\ s^{-1}$) is the diffusion coefficient of
 240 methane in water ($1.76 \cdot 10^{-9}\ m^2\ s^{-1}$ at 25°C and 1 bar [36]). Eq. (9) is adequate for the Graetz
 241 Number (Gz) >4.

242 For the gas phase, k_G is estimated for a stripping process with a shell side and parallel flow of
 243 the gas [37]:

$$244 \quad k_G = 1.25 \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_G}{D_{G,CH_4} \cdot \rho_G} \right)^{0.33} \cdot \left(Re_G \frac{d_e}{L} \right)^{0.93} \quad (10)$$

245 where D_{G,CH_4} ($m^2 s^{-1}$) is the diffusion coefficient of methane through the gas (nitrogen and
 246 water vapour mixture), ρ_G ($kg m^{-3}$) is the gas density, μ_G ($kg m^{-1} s^{-1}$) is the gas viscosity, Re_G
 247 is the Reynold number in the gas phase and d_e (m) is the equivalent diameter.

248 The value of k_m can be estimated by mean of the equation based on the diffusion of the
 249 solutes through the pores without convection [38]:

$$250 \quad k_m = \frac{D_{G,eff} \cdot \varepsilon}{\tau \cdot l} \quad (11)$$

251 where ε , τ and l (m) is the porosity, tortuosity and thickness of the membrane, respectively,
 252 and $D_{G,eff}$ ($m^2 s^{-1}$) is the effective diffusion of the transferred species in the gas phase inside
 253 the pores and can be estimated as follows [39]:

$$254 \quad \frac{1}{D_{G,eff}} = \frac{1}{D_{G,CH_4}} + \frac{1}{D_{G,Kn}} \quad (12)$$

255 where $D_{G,Kn}$ ($m^2 s^{-1}$) is the Knudsen diffusion coefficient of CH_4 through the pores.

256 D_{G,CH_4} was calculated by Eq. (13) to (15) [40,41]:

$$257 \quad D_{G,CH_4} = \frac{1}{\sum_i \frac{y'_i}{D_{CH_4-i}}} \quad (13)$$

$$258 \quad y'_i = \frac{y_i}{1 - y_{CH_4}} \quad (14)$$

$$259 \quad D_{CH_4-i} = \frac{0.01013 \cdot T^{1.75} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{M_i} + \frac{1}{M_{CH_4}} \right)^{1/2}}{P \cdot \left[(\sum v)_i^{1/3} + (\sum v)_{CH_4}^{1/3} \right]^2} \quad (15)$$

260 where i correspond to N_2 or H_2O molecules, y'_i is the mole fraction of specie i evaluated on
261 CH_4 -free basis, D_{CH_4-i} is the binary diffusion coefficient of CH_4 through specie i , T (K) is the
262 temperature, M is the molecular weight, P (Pa) is the pressure in the gas phase and (Σv) is the
263 special atomic diffusion volume (17.90 for N_2 , 12.70 for H_2O and 24.42 for CH_4).

264 $D_{G,Kn}$ was calculated by Eq. (16) [42]:

$$265 \quad D_{G,Kn} = 97 \cdot r_p \cdot \left(\frac{T}{M_{CH_4}} \right)^{1/2} \quad (16)$$

266 where r_p (m) is the pore radius.

267 Finally, $K_{L,est}$ can be calculated as follows [33]:

$$268 \quad \frac{1}{K_{L,est}} = \frac{1}{k_L} + \frac{d_i}{H \cdot k_m \cdot d_{lm}} + \frac{d_i}{H \cdot k_G \cdot d_o} \quad (17)$$

269 where d_{lm} (m) is the logarithmic mean fibre diameter.

270

271 **3. Results and discussion**

272 *3.1. Influence of operational parameters: vacuum pressure and flow-rates of liquid and sweep*
273 *gas.*

274 Experiments with liquid flow-rates (Q_L) of 5.0, 13.7, 21.0 and 28.0 $L h^{-1}$ and with nitrogen
275 sweep gas flow-rates (Q_{N_2}) of 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 $L h^{-1}$ were performed at sweep gas mode ($P_{vac} =$
276 0) and combination mode with vacuum pressures of 100, 200, 400 and 480 mbar. The
277 influence of these parameters on the dissolved methane removal efficiency (RE) and on the
278 content of methane in the recovered gas (C- CH_4) is discussed in this section.

279 As expected, the removal efficiency decreased with the increase in Q_L in combination mode
280 for all the N_2 flow-rates and vacuum pressures. As an example, the results obtained with a N_2

281 flow-rate of 0.5 L h^{-1} are shown in Fig. 3a. This trend can be explained by taking into account
282 the lower residence time for CH_4 inside the fibres [7,11], even though the mass transfer is
283 improved at higher liquid velocities. Operating with a N_2 flow-rate of 0.5 L h^{-1} , the RE
284 decreased from values of around 85 to 89% (for the lowest Q_L of 5.0 L h^{-1}) up to values in the
285 range of 39 to 51% (for the highest Q_L of 28.0 L h^{-1}).

286 The C- CH_4 in the recovered gas was higher with increasing Q_L , for all the Q_{N_2} tested, and the
287 increase of C- CH_4 was more pronounced at low Q_L . For instance, Fig. 3b shows data for a
288 Q_{N_2} of 0.5 L h^{-1} and C- CH_4 values increased from 17 to 21% (for Q_L of 5.0 L h^{-1}) to values of
289 30 to 38% (for Q_L of 13.7 L h^{-1}). For liquid flow-rates higher than 13.7 L h^{-1} , C- CH_4 was
290 always greater than 35% for all of the P_{vac} tested.

291 Experiments with the highest N_2 flow-rates tested (1.0 and 1.5 L h^{-1}) showed the same trends
292 as for a N_2 flow-rate of 0.5 L h^{-1} , although with higher values of RE and lower values of C-
293 CH_4 , as discussed below.

294 In spite of RE decreasing with the Q_L , the estimated total mass flow of recovered methane (R-
295 CH_4) was higher, in agreement with the increase in the C- CH_4 . For example, at P_{vac} of 200
296 mbar and Q_{N_2} of 0.5 L h^{-1} , the estimated mass flow of R- CH_4 ranged from 78 to 201 mg CH_4
297 h^{-1} for Q_L of 5.0 and 28.0 L h^{-1} , respectively (Fig. S1 as supplementary material).

298

299

300 Fig. 3. Effect of liquid flow-rate and vacuum pressure on CH₄ removal efficiency (RE), a) and
 301 c), and on the content of CH₄ in the recovered gas, b) and d), at constant sweep gas flow-rate,
 302 $Q_{N_2} = 0.5 \text{ L h}^{-1}$

303

304 The effect of P_{vac} on RE is shown at different Q_L and a constant N₂ flow-rate of 0.5 L h⁻¹ in
 305 Fig. 3c. The results show that RE continuously increased with P_{vac} as a consequence of greater
 306 driving forces. For example, RE varied from 39% to 51% at P_{vac} of 0 and 480 mbar,
 307 respectively, for Q_L of 28.0 L h⁻¹. Other authors reported the same trend [7,19,43,44]. The
 308 highest increment of RE was generally observed from 0 to 200 mbar of vacuum and, in
 309 contrast, results obtained at 400 and 480 mbar were quite similar. These results show that in
 310 combination mode, greater REs can be obtained than in sweep gas mode (P_{vac} of 0 mbar). At

311 the lowest liquid flow-rate tested (5.0 L h^{-1}), RE increase with the vacuum was the lowest
312 (from 85% to 89% when the vacuum varied from 0 to 480 mbar), so no substantial
313 enhancement under combination mode operation was observed. Increase in RE was more
314 significant when the tested liquid flow-rate increased.

315 For Q_{N_2} higher than 0.5 L h^{-1} (Fig. S2 as supplementary material), the effect of P_{vac} on RE was
316 negligible. For example, at a Q_{N_2} of 1.0 L h^{-1} , RE was kept constant at values around 90%,
317 67% and 56% at Q_L of 5.0, 13.7 and 21.0 L h^{-1} , respectively, for any value of P_{vac} . For a Q_{N_2}
318 of 1.5 L h^{-1} , the same trend with P_{vac} was observed.

319 In Fig. 3d, the general trend of the experimental C- CH_4 in the recovered gas showed a slightly
320 decreased with the vacuum pressure at Q_{N_2} of 0.5 L h^{-1} . This fact can mainly be attributed to
321 the increase of water vapour in the gas phase when the vacuum rises. Typically, membranes
322 used in this kind of application, both microporous and dense membranes, are permeable for
323 water vapour and create a vapour flux through the membrane in the same way as CH_4 [44].
324 Also, other dissolved compounds, such as O_2 and CO_2 , are degassed from the liquid stream
325 and, consequently, involve the dilution of CH_4 in the recovered gas. The results suggest that
326 the composition and hydrophobic character of the membrane play a critical role in bringing
327 down the permeability of water vapour [45–47].

328 Regarding the effect of sweep gas flow-rate, the RE increased with the Q_{N_2} for all the liquid
329 flow-rates and vacuum conditions. Results obtained at 200 mbar and for different Q_L are
330 presented in Fig. 4a. The increase in RE was more significant at low Q_{N_2} . So, at P_{vac} of 200
331 mbar, the RE clearly increased when Q_{N_2} rose from 0.5 to 1.0 L h^{-1} but RE remained almost
332 constant when Q_{N_2} rose from 1.0 to 1.5 L h^{-1} for any liquid flow-rate.

333 C-CH₄ in the recovered gas clearly decreases with Q_{N2} (Fig. 4b), showing a remarkable
 334 dilution effect of the sweep gas. This behaviour was expected, considering the slight effect of
 335 sweep gas flow-rate on the RE, especially for Q_{N2} higher than 1.0 L h⁻¹. Calculated dilution
 336 factors, when doubling the Q_{N2}, were equal to or lower than 1.5. As can be seen in Fig. 4b, to
 337 obtain C-CH₄ values higher than 35%, Q_{N2} lower than or equal to 0.5 L h⁻¹ and Q_L higher than
 338 13.7 L h⁻¹ were needed, which corresponds to RE ranging from 39% to 53% (Fig. 3a). For
 339 higher Q_{N2} values (1.0 and 1.5 L h⁻¹), C-CH₄ in the recovered gas remained below 35% for all
 340 of the liquid flow-rates and vacuum pressures. Despite the low C-CH₄ in the recovered gas at
 341 high Q_{N2}, this gas stream could be mixed with the main biogas stream from an anaerobic
 342 process, maintaining high levels of C-CH₄.

343
 344 *Fig. 4. a) Dissolved CH₄ removal efficiency (RE) and b) content of CH₄ in the recovered gas*
 345 *from the membrane contactor versus sweep gas flow-rate for the combination mode operation*
 346 *at constant vacuum pressure, P_{vac} = 200 mbar*

347
 348 Comparison of these results with those obtained in our previous work [30], carried out with
 349 exactly the same HFMC under similar operational conditions in vacuum mode operation, is
 350 shown in Table 2. Similar RE values can be obtained with a combination of low vacuum and

351 sweep gas flow-rate, rather than using only a high vacuum at any Q_L values. For example, at
 352 Q_L of 5.0 L h⁻¹, RE was 84% in combination mode (with P_{vac} of 100 mbar and Q_{N_2} of 0.5 L h⁻¹
 353 ¹) whilst a P_{vac} of 500 mbar was necessary to obtain a similar RE (82%) when only using
 354 vacuum at Q_L of 4.1 L h⁻¹. For low vacuum values (100 to 140 mbar), the application of a
 355 simultaneous low Q_{N_2} of 0.5 L h⁻¹ increased RE from 69% to 84% and from 32% to 42%, for
 356 low and high Q_L , respectively. These results demonstrate the potential enhancement of the
 357 driving force caused by the additive effect of the combination of vacuum and sweep gas.

358 *Table 2. Comparison of methane removal efficiency obtained in vacuum (Henares et al. [30])*
 359 *and combination mode (this work)*

Q_L , L h ⁻¹	Q_{N_2} , L h ⁻¹	P_{vac} , mbar	RE, %	Reference
4.1	-	500	82	[30]
27.2	-	500	45	[30]
4.1	-	140	69	[30]
27.2	-	140	32	[30]
5.0	0.5	100	84	This work
28.0	0.5	100	42	This work

360

361 The highest REs obtained in this work (~90%) were achieved for the minimum Q_L (5.0 L h⁻¹),
 362 and values of P_{vac} and Q_{N_2} higher than 100 mbar and 0.5 L h⁻¹, respectively. However, the
 363 increase of these parameter values from P_{vac} 200 mbar or Q_{N_2} 1.0 L h⁻¹ did not improve the
 364 efficiency of the process, significantly. This shows that, from a practical point of view, a
 365 combination of intermediate values of P_{vac} and Q_{N_2} would be the most suitable operational
 366 conditions.

367 Similar RE values (~90%) have been previously reported for sweep gas or vacuum operations
 368 with porous and dense membrane contactors [7,19,21,22]. As an example, Cookney et al. [22]
 369 obtained maximum RE values of 93% and 99% for a PDMS (dense) and PP (microporous)
 370 HFMC, respectively, operating in sweep gas mode with v_L of 0.04 cm s⁻¹ (Q_L calculated as

371 0.2 and 0.4 L h⁻¹, respectively) and v_G of 33.00 and 19.00 cm s⁻¹ (Q_{N2} calculated as 330.0 and
372 610.0 L h⁻¹, respectively). In general, the highest RE values have been reported in sweep gas
373 operations and these values of RE can only be obtained with high vacuum values (800 to 950
374 mbar) [11,14,30,43]. For instance, Bandara et al. [11] obtained a maximum RE of 86% in
375 vacuum mode with P_{vac} of 800 mbar and Q_L of 0.1 L h⁻¹ (v_L of 0.02 cm s⁻¹) and a composite,
376 dense membrane.

377

378 3.2. Gas-to-liquid ratio analysis

379 Gas-to-liquid ratio (G/L) is defined as follows (with flow-rates measured at atmospheric
380 pressure):

$$381 \quad G/L = \frac{Q_{N_2}}{Q_L} \quad (18)$$

382 Increasing G/L involves a higher driving force and, consequently, major RE are obtained (Fig.
383 5a). At the lowest Q_{N2} value of 0.5 L h⁻¹ (open symbols) a significant increase in RE was
384 observed when P_{vac} was increased for the same G/L ratio. For example, at a G/L ratio of
385 0.037, RE values of 60% and 65% were obtained for P_{vac} of 200 and 400 mbar, respectively.
386 In contrast, for a higher Q_{N2} of 1.0 L h⁻¹ (filled grey symbols) and G/L of 0.048, the results
387 showed similar REs independent of P_{vac} for all Q_L tested. Thus, the application of vacuum
388 improved removal performance when using 0.5 L h⁻¹ at all G/L ratios but, at higher Q_{N2}, the
389 application of vacuum did not significantly increase RE, in agreement with previous findings.

390 In the case of C-CH₄ (Fig. 5b), a notable effect of G/L was observed, especially at low G/L
391 (<0.050). The maximum C-CH₄ obtained was 45% for the minimum G/L tested (0.012) and
392 without vacuum in the gas line. Generally, no notable effect of P_{vac} in the final C-CH₄ was
393 observed for any G/L tested. The decrease of the C-CH₄ with G/L followed a power

394 regression equation, indicating the high sensitivity of the C-CH₄ in the recovered gas at low
395 values of G/L, especially between 0.010 and 0.050.

396

397 Fig. 5. a) Dissolved CH₄ removal efficiency (RE) with $Q_{N_2} = 0.5 \text{ L h}^{-1}$ (open symbols), $Q_{N_2} =$
398 1.0 L h^{-1} (filled grey symbols) and $Q_{N_2} = 1.5 \text{ L h}^{-1}$ (filled black symbols) and b) content of CH₄
399 in the recovered gas from the membrane contactor versus gas-to-liquid ratio (G/L) for the
400 combination mode operation at different vacuum pressures

401

402 According to the results, the maximum G/L which allows us to obtain C-CH₄ values higher
403 than 35%, in order to efficiently produce electricity from the recovered gas, was 0.030 with
404 REs between 50% and 55%. From a theoretical point of view and taking into account Henry's
405 Law, for a G/L of 0.030, a maximum RE value of ~90% could be obtained [21]. As in our
406 case, reported experimental RE values are often far from this maximum theoretical value
407 [21,22,48].

408 A compromise between the final C-CH₄ and RE achieved should be required for a proper
409 optimisation of the process, from an energetic point of view. In this regard, the use of several
410 membranes coupled in series has been proposed as an alternative to achieve higher overall
411 REs for the lowest G/L [22,28,49]. For example, Martić et al. [28] used three HFMC, coupled

412 in series in combination mode for O₂ removal at a G/L of 0.3 and P_{vac} of 200 mbar; an overall
413 RE value of ~99% was reported.

414

415 3.3. Mass transfer analysis

416 The obtained results seem to point to the fact that the mass transfer resistance of the gas phase
417 was usually negligible, since the dependence of RE on P_{vac} and on sweep gas flow-rate was
418 relatively low, especially at the highest vacuum and flow-rate (Fig. 4a). This suggests that,
419 under these conditions, the limiting mass transfer resistance is mainly located in the liquid
420 phase.

421 This fact is in agreement with the theoretical estimation of the three individual mass transfer
422 resistances, obtained from equations (9) to (17). In this regard, R_{L,est} values range from
423 $1.7 \cdot 10^5 \text{ s m}^{-3}$ to $2.9 \cdot 10^5 \text{ s m}^{-3}$ for the studied conditions, which represents at least 98.74% of
424 the overall estimated resistance (R_{ov,est}). R_m and R_G were always below 0.01% and 1.0%,
425 respectively, which is similar to those obtained by Rongwong et al. [19] for a porous
426 polyimide membrane. Membrane mass transfer resistance has been also estimated using the
427 Wilson plot method (Supplementary material S3) with similar results. Therefore, the
428 estimated values of R_{m,est} and R_{G,est} are negligible compared with R_{L,est} and, consequently, it
429 can be assumed that R_{ov,est} \approx R_{L,est}. These results are in agreement with most previous studies
430 of methane degassing [7,14,19,22,44–46], where the theoretical resistance to mass transfer
431 was mainly located in the liquid phase.

432 Estimated (R_{ov,est}) and experimental (R_{ov,exp}) overall mass transfer resistance results are
433 compared and shown in Fig. 6a. At the lowest Q_{N2} studied, R_{ov,exp} ranged from $3.37 \cdot 10^5 \text{ s m}^{-3}$,
434 for Q_L of 5.0 L h⁻¹ and P_{vac} of 200 mbar, to $1.18 \cdot 10^5 \text{ s m}^{-3}$, for Q_L of 28.0 L h⁻¹ and P_{vac} of 0

435 mbar, with a significant influence of the liquid flow-rate and an almost negligible impact of
 436 the vacuum pressure. No noticeable difference in the mass transfer resistance was observed
 437 between the combination and sweep gas modes (P_{vac} of 0 mbar). Similar values and trends
 438 were obtained for the higher Q_{N_2} studied (Fig. 6b). It is important to point out that most of the
 439 experimental values were slightly higher than the estimated values (Fig. 6a), especially at low
 440 liquid flow-rates for the lowest Q_{N_2} studied (Fig. 6b). These results seem to indicate that gas
 441 phase resistance could be underestimated for the lowest Q_{N_2} studied.

442

443 *Fig. 6. Comparison of the experimental (open symbols) and estimated (black line) overall*
 444 *mass transfer resistance (R_{ov}) versus a) liquid flow-rate at $Q_{N_2} = 0.5 \text{ L h}^{-1}$ and different*
 445 *vacuum pressures and b) sweep gas flow-rate at $P_{vac} = 200 \text{ mbar}$ and different liquid flow-*
 446 *rates*

447

448 Comparing the results from this work in combination mode with those previously obtained
 449 operating in vacuum mode [30], lower $R_{ov,exp}$ was usually obtained in combination mode than
 450 in vacuum mode, mainly due to the absence of wetting (membrane pores totally or partially
 451 filled with liquid phase). Wetting phenomenon involves an additional resistance located in the
 452 membrane phase with an increase of the pressure into the lumen side being in agreement with

453 the rise of the liquid flow-rate. In combination mode, the wetting phenomenon was not
454 observed, at least not in the range of the values tested, in contrast to when vacuum mode was
455 operated under similar conditions [30]. It seems that the presence of sweep gas involves an
456 additional effect on the membrane surface, avoiding the overcoming of the critical
457 transmembrane pressure [29,45,50].

458 In Table 3, our $K_{L,exp}$ can be compared with that reported in previous studies carried out with
459 different microporous HFMC, operated in sweep gas mode and on the lumen side. No
460 significant differences were observed for $K_{L,exp}$ between the different experiments for
461 polypropylene HFMCs and similar liquid velocities. No significant effects of the gas velocity
462 were observed on $K_{L,exp}$, which is in agreement with the negligible resistance of the gas phase.
463 The greater reported values of $K_{L,exp}$ for the polyamide HFMC (66% of porosity), rather than
464 for the PP HFMC (around 40% of porosity), seem to indicate an important role of the
465 membrane properties, especially its porosity. In this case, greater $K_{L,exp}$ values were observed
466 with a higher porosity.

467 From the scarcity of papers found in the literature, regarding combination mode,
468 Kartohardjono's work can be highlighted. For removal of O_2 , Kartohardjono et al. [27]
469 obtained $K_{L,exp}$ values ranging from $10 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ to $35 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ at liquid velocities varying
470 between 35 and 80 cm s^{-1} and with a PP membrane operating in combination mode and liquid
471 flowing through the shell side.

472

473

474

475

476 *Table 3. Summary of overall mass transfer coefficients from different authors for methane*
 477 *recovery from liquid effluents operating in sweep gas mode and lumen side with microporous*
 478 *degassing membranes. Combination mode with P_{vac} ranging from 0 to 480 mbar in this work*

Effluent	Membrane	$v_L, \text{cm s}^{-1}$ ($Q_L, \text{L h}^{-1}$)	$v_G, \text{cm s}^{-1}$ ($Q_{N_2}, \text{L h}^{-1}$)	$K_L \cdot 10^5, \text{m s}^{-1}$	Reference
Saturated water	PP	1.59 – 8.90 (5.0 – 28.0)	0.04 – 0.13 (0.5 – 1.5)	1.65 – 3.67	This work
EGSB	PP	1.27 – 8.58 (4.1 – 27.0)	2.20 – 67.69 (26 – 800)	1.94 – 3.74	[30]
Saturated water	PP	1.20 – 4.50 (12.2 – 45.6)	18.61 (600)	1.56 – 2.14	[22]
Saturated water	PP	11.84 (120)	1.86 – 18.61 (60 – 600)	1.20 – 1.54	[21]
Saturated water	Polyamide	9.19 – 31.52 (0.7 – 2.4)	1.28 (1.2)	4.84 – 7.83	[19]

479

480 3.4. Energy analysis

481 In order to determine the feasibility of the operation in terms of its energy requirements, an
 482 energy analysis was carried out, assuming that the main energy consumption was related to
 483 the pumps (vacuum and liquid) and the efficiency of the combustion of methane should be
 484 decreased by around 20% due to the dilution effect of the sweep gas.

485 The energy consumption of the vacuum pump (W_{vp} , J/s) was estimated for the adiabatic
 486 compression process (a common, polytropic compression [6]) by using the following equation
 487 [9]:

$$488 \quad W_{vp} = \frac{F_{G,tot} \cdot R \cdot T_G \cdot \gamma}{(1-\gamma) \cdot \eta_{vp}} \left(\frac{P_{G,out}}{P_{G,in}}^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right) \quad (19)$$

489 where $F_{G,tot}$ (mol s^{-1}) is the molar flow-rate of the recovered gas, R ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) is the gas
 490 constant with a value of 8.314, T_G (K) is the gas temperature, $P_{G,in}$ and $P_{G,out}$ (Pa) are the
 491 pressure in the suction and discharge ports of the vacuum pump, respectively, and γ and η_{vp}
 492 are the estimated adiabatic coefficient and vacuum pump efficiency, respectively [48].

493 The energy consumption of the liquid pump (W_{lp} , J/s) used to drive the liquid and overcome
 494 the pressure drop (ΔP_L , Pa) along the HFMC can be estimated as follows [9]:

$$495 \quad W_{lp} = \frac{Q_l \cdot \Delta P_L}{\eta_{lp}} \quad (20)$$

496 where Q_l ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$) is the flow-rate of the liquid pump and η_{lp} is the pump efficiency, assumed
 497 to be equal at 65%. The pressure drop estimation is based on the Hagen-Poiseuille equation
 498 [48]:

$$499 \quad \Delta P_L = \frac{8 \cdot \mu_w \cdot v_L \cdot L}{d_i^2} \quad (21)$$

500 where μ_w ($\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) is the viscosity of water.

501 The normalized energy consumption (sum of vacuum and liquid pumps) is expressed per
 502 gram of recovered CH_4 and m^3 of the treated water, taking into account the quantity of
 503 methane recovered in each experiment and the liquid-flow rate. Results are shown in Fig. 7.
 504 For the lowest liquid flow-rate ($Q_L=5.0 \text{ L h}^{-1}$), the normalized energy consumption was highly
 505 dependent on the vacuum pressure, since the energy consumed in the vacuum device was the
 506 major contribution, which accounted for around 50% and 90% of the total energy
 507 consumption for P_{vac} of 100 and 480 mbar, respectively. For higher values of Q_L , energy
 508 consumption resulted in values around $1.90 \cdot 10^3 \text{ kJ g}^{-1} \text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3}$ (mean values of $1.89 \pm 0.66 \cdot 10^3$,
 509 $1.90 \pm 0.19 \cdot 10^3$ and $1.94 \pm 0.01 \cdot 10^3 \text{ kJ g}^{-1} \text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3}$, for Q_L of 13.7, 21.0 y 28.0 L h^{-1} ,
 510 respectively), and for all the Q_{N_2} tested. For the lowest Q_L (5.0 L h^{-1}), the increase in the

511 sweep gas flow-rate resulted in an increase in the normalized energy consumption, attributed
 512 again to the low consumption of the liquid pump in comparison with the vacuum device.

513
 514 *Fig. 7. Energy consumption per gram of CH₄ and m³ of treated effluent versus a) liquid flow-*
 515 *rate (at constant sweep gas flow-rate, $Q_{N_2} = 0.5 \text{ L h}^{-1}$, and different vacuum pressure) and b)*
 516 *sweep gas flow-rate (at constant vacuum pressure, $P_{\text{vac}} = 200 \text{ mbar}$, and different liquid flow-*
 517 *rates).*

518 For energy production, a combustion heat for CH₄ of 38 MJ m⁻³ (at 25°C and 1 atm) was
 519 assumed [51]. Electrical efficiencies of around 35% are usually reported for biogas in
 520 microturbines but, taking into account the fact that the concentration of methane was lower
 521 than in reactor biogas (mainly due to the dilution of sweep gas), a decrease of around 20% has
 522 been applied in the efficiency of the combustion process.

523 Finally, the net recovered energy (Net E, kJ m⁻³) was obtained from the difference between
 524 the energy produced in a microturbine and total energy consumption by the pumps. Net E is
 525 expressed for 1 m³ of the liquid treated.

526

527 *Fig. 8. Net energy obtained from the combustion of methane recovered in the membrane*
 528 *contactor for the treatment of 1 m³ of effluent (Net E) versus a) liquid flow-rate (at constant*
 529 *sweep gas flow-rate, $Q_{N2} = 0.5 \text{ L h}^{-1}$, and different vacuum pressure) and b) sweep gas flow-*
 530 *rate (at constant vacuum pressure, $P_{vac} = 200 \text{ mbar}$, and different liquid flow-rates)*

531

532 The energy analysis showed a positive net recovered energy under all operating conditions
 533 (Fig. 8a). The maximum Net E recovered was 270 kJ m⁻³, which resulted in a net recovered
 534 energy of CH₄ of $6.31 \cdot 10^3 \text{ kJ g}^{-1}\text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3}$, for Q_{N2} of 1.5 L h⁻¹ and Q_L of 5.0 L h⁻¹ with P_{vac} of
 535 200 mbar (Fig. 8b). In these conditions (Q_{N2} > 0.5 L h⁻¹ and Q_L < 13.7 L h⁻¹), C-CH₄ values
 536 are lower than 35%, thus the recovered gas should be mixed with a main biogas stream from
 537 the anaerobic process in order to recover the maximum energy from the R-CH₄ for electricity
 538 production. In the case of the direct use of the recovered gas in a microturbine (35% C-CH₄),
 539 the actual maximum Net E was 145 kJ m⁻³ ($2.37 \cdot 10^3 \text{ kJ g}^{-1}\text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3}$) when Q_{N2} and Q_L were
 540 0.5 L h⁻¹ and 13.7 L h⁻¹, respectively, without vacuum. When Q_L was 21.0 and 28.0 L h⁻¹ the
 541 maximum Net E was obtained at P_{vac} of 200 mbar with values of 126 and 103 kJ m⁻³ ($1.49 \cdot 10^3$
 542 and $0.98 \cdot 10^3 \text{ kJ g}^{-1}\text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3}$), respectively. The reduction of Net E with the Q_L (Fig. 8a) was a
 543 consequence of the lower REs associated with higher liquid velocities (Fig. 3a). The applied
 544 vacuum for the extraction of CH₄ did not show a significant effect on Net E. Net E results

545 were in concordance with theoretical estimations, which predicted a maximum Net E of 178
546 kJ m^{-3} at P_{vac} of 100 mbar and Q_{N_2} of 6.6 L h^{-1} [48] and a carbon neutral process [14,21].

547 The Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) of an anaerobic digestion of wastewater sludge with
548 dissolved methane recovery was calculated according to the cost metric methodology used by
549 the International Renewable Energy Agency [52]. For LCOE calculations, standardized
550 assumptions values for bioenergy production technologies in OECD countries were used [52].
551 A scheme of the process and its specific values can be found as Supplementary material (S4).
552 LCOE resulted in a value of 79 € MWh^{-1} similar to those obtained for bioenergy plants in
553 Europe with values ranging from 50 to 100 € MWh^{-1} [52]. Implementation of the membrane
554 contactor system for dissolved CH_4 recovery does not significantly increase the LCOE value.

555

556 **4. Conclusions**

557 The removal and recovery of dissolved methane from water by means of a microporous
558 polypropylene hollow fibre membrane contactor, operating in combination mode (vacuum
559 and nitrogen as sweep gas, simultaneously), showed significantly greater removal efficiencies
560 of methane and lower mass transfer resistances than independent operational modes in
561 practically all operational conditions. The maximum removal efficiency observed was higher
562 than 90% in soft operational conditions (low nitrogen flow-rate and vacuum) and a G/L ratio
563 from 0.20.

564 An increase of methane content in the recovered gas was observed with a rise in liquid flow-
565 rate. On the contrary, the methane content was not significantly affected by the vacuum
566 pressure which could be due to the presence of other desorbed gases. A gas composition

567 higher than 35% of methane was achieved at the lowest G/L ratios (< 0.03) and moderate
568 vacuum (< 200 mbar).

569 The mass transfer analysis showed that wetting phenomenon did not take place in
570 combination mode in the operational conditions tested. The main mass transfer resistance was
571 located in the liquid phase with negligible resistances of the gas phase and microporous
572 membrane.

573 The energy balance showed that the energy production from recovered methane was greater
574 than the energy consumption by the degasification process in all experiments, allowing a self-
575 sufficient process. The influence of vacuum pressure on the net produced energy was
576 negligible due to the rise of removal efficiency of methane and energy consumption of the
577 vacuum pump, simultaneously. The maximum net energy obtained was 270 kJ m^{-3} of treated
578 effluent at G/L of 0.30 and moderate vacuum of 200 mbar.

579 Combination mode can enhance the performance of the membrane contactor to recover
580 dissolved methane from anaerobic effluent, reducing the carbon footprint of an anaerobic
581 wastewater treatment plant by using this methane for electricity or heat production.

582

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588

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Supplementary Material for

Simultaneous application of vacuum and sweep gas in a polypropylene membrane contactor for the recovery of dissolved methane from water

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S1. Estimated mass flow of recovered methane (R-CH₄)

Influence of liquid flow-rate (Q_L , L h⁻¹) on the estimated mass flow of recovered methane (mg CH₄ h⁻¹) at sweep gas flow-rate (Q_{N_2} , L h⁻¹) of 0.5 L h⁻¹. Calculations were made based on liquid mass balance.

Fig. S1. Estimated mass flow of recovered methane (R-CH₄) versus liquid flow-rate for the combination mode operation with $Q_{N_2} = 0.5$ L h⁻¹.

S2. Effect of vacuum pressure

Influence of vacuum pressure (P_{vac} , mbar) on methane removal efficiency (RE, %) and content of methane in the recovered gas from the membrane contactor at sweep gas flow-rate (Q_{N_2} , $L h^{-1}$) higher than $0.5 L h^{-1}$.

Fig. S2. a) Dissolved CH_4 removal efficiency (RE, %) and b) content of CH_4 in the recovered gas from de membrane contactor versus vacuum pressure for the combination mode operation with $Q_{N_2} = 1.0 L h^{-1}$.

S3. Wilson's Plot Analysis

A Wilson's Plot analysis was carried out in order to estimate the mass transfer coefficient (k_m , m s^{-1}) of the PP membrane (Fig. S3). Assuming a negligible gas phase resistance, the results listed in Table S1 indicate a negligible mass transfer resistance of the membrane ($R_m \ll R_L$).

Fig. S3. Wilson's Plot Analysis from the mass transfer data obtained for the combination mode operation with $Q_{N_2} = 0.5 \text{ L h}^{-1}$ as a function of the liquid velocity and the parameter α .

Table S1. Details of the Wilson's Plot Analysis and the obtained mass transfer coefficients and resistances of the PP membrane at different vacuum pressures for the combination mode operation with $Q_{N_2} = 0.5 \text{ L h}^{-1}$ and liquid flow-rates between 5.0 and 28.0 L h^{-1} .

$P_{\text{vac}}, \text{ mbar}$	α	R^2	$k_m \cdot 10^2, \text{ m s}^{-1}$	$R_m, \text{ s m}^{-3}$
100	0.39	0.993	2.62	5.46
200	0.42	0.998	3.21	4.94
400	0.41	0.993	2.88	4.98
480	0.35	0.961	2.42	4.47

S4. Levelized Cost of Energy Analysis (LCOE)

The Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) of an energy plant based on an anaerobic digestion of wastewater sludge with dissolved methane recovery was calculated. A scheme of the process and detailed values are shown in Fig. S4.

Fig. S4. Scheme of an energy plant integrated in an anaerobic digester of wastewater sludge (from an urban wastewater treatment plant) with a dissolved methane recovery system by membrane contactors, and values used for Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) calculation. (TSS and VSS: total and volatile suspended solid respectively, RE: dissolved methane removal efficiency, Net E: net energy recovered from methane, η : microturbine efficiency for electricity conversion)

LCOE value was calculated according to the cost metric methodology used by the International Renewable Energy Agency [1], using the following equation:

$$\text{LCOE} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{I_t + M_t + F_t}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{E_t}{(1+r)^t}} \quad (\text{S1})$$

where I_t is investment cost in the year t , M_t is the operation and maintenance costs in the year t , F_t is the fuel cost in the year t , E_t is the electricity generation in the year t , r is the discount rate and n is the economic life of the plant.

For LCOE calculations, standardized assumptions values for bioenergy production technologies in OECD countries were used [1] with a capacity factor of 85% and an economic life of the plant of 20 years. LCOE value of the studied process resulted in 79 € MWh⁻¹.

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